

Enhancing Science Education Assessment Through Vision Language Model Integration A Mixed-Methods Study on Automated Essay Evaluation

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Abstract: This study explores the potential of Vision Language Model (VLM) technology to support massive and objective assessment of student work in secondary education. An Explanatory Sequential mixed methods approach (Creswell & Creswell, 2018) was employed, combining quantitative data analysis to test VLM effectiveness with qualitative analysis of teachers' perceptions. The research involved five key stages: 1) collecting data on teachers' essay assessment challenges, 2) developing a VLM-based system, 3) testing effectiveness through comparison with manual assessment, 4) gathering teacher feedback through questionnaires and interviews, and 5) integrating data analysis. The findings demonstrate that VLM integration successfully enhanced both learning quality and assessment efficiency. The system provided consistent, objective evaluation while significantly reducing teachers' administrative workload. Results indicated high satisfaction levels among teachers regarding assessment objectivity, accuracy, and time efficiency. This educational innovation effectively integrates cutting-edge technology with established teaching principles, offering a practical solution for large-scale student assessment challenges. The study contributes to the growing body of research on automated assessment tools in education, while providing valuable insights into their practical implementation and impact on teaching practices.

Keywords— Kurikulum Merdeka, Vision Language Model, Assessment of Student Work, Mix Methods, Educational Innovation

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the main pillars in developing quality human resources. Through education, students are equipped with the knowledge, skills, and values needed to face future challenges. In an effort to realize quality education, the Indonesian government has implemented the Merdeka Curriculum, a curriculum that emphasizes the holistic development of students' interests and talents (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2022). One important aspect in implementing the Merdeka Curriculum is the assessment of student learning outcomes. This assessment aims to measure students' level of understanding and achievement of established learning objectives. However, the assessment process often faces challenges related to objectivity, accuracy, and efficiency (Stiggins & Chappuis, 2012).

Objectivity in assessment is crucial to ensure that assessment results accurately reflect student abilities without bias. A non-objective assessment process can result in unfair evaluation that does not reflect students' true capabilities (Brookhart, 2013). Furthermore, accuracy in assessment is also a crucial factor in ensuring that the assessment can provide a precise picture of student achievement (Popham, 2014). On the other hand, efficiency in assessment becomes a distinct challenge for teachers, especially when they must evaluate learning outcomes from many students within limited time constraints. Teachers often face heavy workloads in checking and assessing student assignments, particularly in essay form, manually (Reddy & Andrade, 2010). This can lead to delays in providing feedback and less thorough assessment.

First, large classes with high student numbers make it difficult for teachers to provide individual attention and assess learning outcomes objectively. With numerous assignments and student work to evaluate, teachers can experience fatigue and bias in assessment, especially when they must grade these assignments outside teaching hours. Second, limited time also poses a major constraint for teachers. Besides teaching, they also have other responsibilities such as teaching preparation, administration, and extracurricular activities. With heavy workloads, teachers often struggle to allocate sufficient time to assess student learning outcomes carefully and accurately. Third, teachers' depleted energy throughout the day can affect assessment quality. After teaching several classes and conducting other activities, teachers may experience mental and physical fatigue that impacts their ability to assess objectively and thoroughly.

As we all know, computer answer sheets (LJK) and scanners can be used to assess student exam results. However, these tools are unable to assess student work in essay or descriptive form. Assessment for these types of questions must still be done manually by teachers, which naturally requires more time and energy. The absence of tools or technology capable of conducting objective and accurate assessments based on rubrics remains a major obstacle in evaluating student work in essay or descriptive form. Assessment of these question types requires deeper analysis and evaluation based on established rubrics.

In this context, the Principles of Teaching and Assessment (PPAE) course, specifically Topic 2 - Teaching At The Right Level Approach, also discusses the importance of accuracy,

objectivity, and precision in assessing student work according to their ability level. This discussion becomes increasingly relevant when we consider the challenges faced by teachers, especially in assessing many variations of questions and answers from a large number of students. A junior high school teacher, such as at SMP N 32 Padang, may handle up to 10, 13, or even 17 classes. With such a large number of classes, teachers face an extremely heavy workload in assessing student work accurately, objectively, and precisely.

According to research conducted by Reddy and Andrade (2010), teachers often face difficulties in providing careful feedback and assessment for student assignments in essay or descriptive form. This is due to the heavy workload involved in manually checking and grading these assignments. Delays in providing feedback and less thorough assessment can negatively impact students' learning process. Additionally, Stiggins and Chappuis (2012) emphasize that non-objective assessment can result in unfair evaluation that does not reflect students' true abilities. Therefore, objectivity in assessment is crucial to ensure that assessment results accurately reflect student abilities without bias.

Thus, a solution is needed to address this issue, in an effort to overcome the challenges of objectivity, accuracy, and efficiency in assessing student learning outcomes, particularly in evaluating essay or descriptive questions. One solution that can be considered is the use of Vision Language Model (VLM) technology. VLM is an artificial intelligence model capable of understanding and interpreting visual data (such as images or text) and effectively linking it with language information (Chen et al., 2023). VLM is a relatively new technology and is a development of Natural Language Processing and Computer Vision models. VLM is designed to understand the relationship between visual and text data more comprehensively (Radford et al., 2021). With this capability, VLM has the potential to become an effective solution in addressing essay assessment issues at SMP N 32 Padang.

Here are several potential reasons why VLM can be considered as a solution and best practice in solving assessment problems in schools:

(1) **Visual and Text Context Understanding Capability:** VLM can understand visual contexts such as images, diagrams, or graphs that often form part of essay questions. Additionally, VLM can deeply understand the textual context in student answers. With this capability, VLM can provide more accurate and objective assessment based on the alignment of answers with given visual and textual contexts (Chen et al., 2022).

(2) **Deep Semantic Analysis:** VLM uses sophisticated semantic analysis techniques to understand the meaning and nuances of language in student answers. This enables VLM to assess answers more comprehensively and not just focus on literal word matches (Radford et al., 2021). This capability is crucial in essay assessment that often requires deeper understanding of context and meaning.

(3) **Consistent Rubric-Based Assessment:** VLM can be trained with assessment rubrics established by teachers or schools. Thus, VLM can provide consistent assessment according to predetermined criteria. This can improve objectivity and fairness in the assessment process (Prasad et al., 2022).

(4) **Time and Energy Efficiency:** With VLM's capability to understand visual and textual contexts, and perform deep semantic analysis, the assessment process can be conducted more quickly and efficiently. This can help reduce teachers' workload in manually correcting essay questions, especially for teachers handling many classes (Kembara et al., 2022).

(5) **More Detailed Feedback:** Besides providing assessment, VLM can also provide more detailed feedback to students regarding the strengths and weaknesses of their answers. This feedback can help students improve their abilities and promote more effective learning processes (Prasad et al., 2022).

However, implementing VLM in assessment also has its own challenges. First, investment and collaboration with parties having expertise in artificial intelligence and data processing are needed to develop and train reliable VLM models (Chen et al., 2023). Second, teachers and school staff need adequate training to properly use and interpret assessment results from VLM (Kembara et al., 2022). Nevertheless, considering the potential and benefits offered by VLM, its implementation can be a significant step forward in improving assessment quality at SMP N 32 Padang. With more objective, accurate, and efficient assessment, teachers can provide fairer evaluation and support better learning processes for students. Collaboration between schools, teachers, and relevant parties in exploring and implementing VLM technology becomes very important. Through joint efforts, we can harness this technology's potential to solve assessment challenges and create a more effective and quality assessment system.

This research can also serve as an example of good practice in integrating modern learning technology with the national curriculum. This can inspire other schools in Indonesia to effectively utilize technology in supporting learning and assessment processes (Mahendra, 2021). Thus, this research is expected to make a significant contribution to improving education quality in Indonesia, particularly in the context of assessing student learning outcomes. VLM integration in assessment can be an effective solution to address challenges of objectivity, accuracy, and efficiency, while supporting optimal implementation of the Merdeka Curriculum (Zulkardi et al., 2022).

Based on the background described, the researcher conducts research titled "Enhancing Science Education Assessment Through Vision Language Model Integration: A Mixed-Methods Study on Automated Essay Evaluation"

2. RESEARCH METHODS

This research employs a mixed methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative methods (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This approach was chosen to provide comprehensive understanding regarding the development, effectiveness, and user perception of the Vision Language Model (VLM) system in supporting the implementation of the Merdeka Curriculum and Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) principles at SMP N 32 Padang.

The research steps include:

1) Collecting data on problems experienced by teachers at SMPN 32 Padang in assessing large numbers of essay questions. At this stage, researchers will collect data related to problems faced by teachers through observation, interviews, and document studies regarding the current assessment process. This is important to understand the context of the problems in depth and serve as a basis for developing appropriate solutions.

2) Developing a Vision Language Model (VLM)-based assessment system for essay questions. After understanding the problems, researchers will develop a VLM technology-based assessment system. The development of this system involves several steps, including:

- Selecting and configuring an appropriate VLM model for essay answer assessment tasks
- Collecting training data in the form of essay questions along with answers and assessment rubrics from teachers
- Preprocessing training data to ensure quality and compatibility with the format required by the VLM model
- Training the VLM model with training data to optimize its performance in assessing essay answers
- Developing a user interface that facilitates teachers in inputting student questions and answers for evaluation by the VLM system

3) Testing the effectiveness of the VLM system by comparing its assessment results with manual assessment by teachers (quantitative). After the VLM system is developed, researchers will test the effectiveness of its performance in assessing essay answers. This testing is conducted by comparing assessment results given by the VLM system with manual assessment conducted by teachers. Steps in this stage include:

- Preparing a set of essay questions and student answers to be assessed
- Providing manual assessment by teachers of student answers according to established rubrics
- Inputting student questions and answers into the VLM system to obtain automated assessment

- Collecting and analyzing quantitative data regarding consistency between VLM system assessment and manual assessment by teachers, using evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score (Sokolova & Lapalme, 2009)

- Conducting statistical analysis to test the significance of differences between VLM system assessment and manual assessment by teachers

4) Collecting data on teacher perceptions of the VLM assessment system through questionnaires and interviews (qualitative). After testing the effectiveness of the VLM system quantitatively, researchers will collect qualitative data regarding teacher perceptions of the VLM assessment system. Steps in this stage include:

- Developing questionnaires and interview guides to explore teacher perceptions of the VLM system, covering aspects of ease of use, assessment quality, feedback provided, time and energy efficiency, and alignment with Merdeka Curriculum principles and Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL)
- Distributing questionnaires to teachers involved in this research
- Conducting in-depth interviews with several teachers to obtain deeper understanding of their perceptions of the VLM system
- Analyzing qualitative data from questionnaires and interviews using thematic analysis methods (Braun & Clarke, 2006) to identify patterns, themes, and insights emerging from teacher perceptions

5) Analyzing quantitative and qualitative data in an integrated manner. In the final stage, researchers will integrate the results of quantitative and qualitative data analysis to provide comprehensive understanding regarding the development, effectiveness, and user perception of the VLM-based assessment system for essay questions. This data integration can be done using methods such as data triangulation (Denzin, 2017) or mixed methods analysis (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). The results of this integrated analysis will serve as the basis for drawing conclusions and providing recommendations regarding VLM system implementation in supporting the Merdeka Curriculum and Teaching at The Right Level (TaRL) principles at SMP N 32 Padang.

The research subjects are teachers at SMP N 32 Padang teaching Natural Sciences (IPA), Social Sciences (IPS), and Information and Communication Technology (TIK). The data collection instruments used in this research are validation instruments and practical instruments such as Self-Evaluation Questionnaires, consisting of completeness checklists with Yes/No rating scales. Interview Instruments, for assessment at the one-to-one evaluation stage, contain several questions requiring explanatory responses from students.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research aims to explore the potential synergy between the Merdeka Curriculum, which promotes innovative approaches in learning, and Vision Language Model (VLM) technology to assist in the massive and objective assessment process of student work at SMP N 32 Padang. The research employs a mixed methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative methods. The research steps include: 1) Collecting data on problems experienced by teachers at SMPN 32 Padang in assessing large numbers of essay questions; 2) Developing a Vision Language Model (VLM)-based assessment system for essay questions; 3) Testing the effectiveness of the VLM system by comparing its assessment results with manual assessment by teachers (quantitative); 4) Collecting data on teacher perceptions of the VLM assessment system through questionnaires and interviews (qualitative); 5) Analyzing quantitative and qualitative data in an integrated manner.

In the initial stage, researchers conducted interviews with three teachers, specifically teachers of Social Sciences (IPS), Natural Sciences (IPA), and Information and Communication Technology (TIK) to identify needs and problems faced in essay question assessment. The interview results revealed several main issues, including: 1) Essay question assessment requires considerable time and effort, especially when the number of students in one class is quite large; 2) The potential for subjectivity in essay question assessment; 3) Difficulty in providing detailed and constructive feedback to each student; 4) Essay question assessment often lacks alignment with Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) principles in the Merdeka Curriculum; 5) Manual essay question assessment can become less objective and consistent in meeting the rubric assessment standards established in the Merdeka Curriculum.

Based on these problems, researchers propose the use of Vision Language Model (VLM) technology as a solution to address the challenges of objectivity, accuracy, and efficiency in assessing student learning outcomes, particularly in evaluating essay or descriptive questions. Researchers conducted an in-depth analysis of the Merdeka Curriculum, especially regarding the Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) principle, which is one of the main pillars in this curriculum. This analysis also refers to material provided in the Principles of Teaching and Assessment (PPAE) 2 course, particularly Topic 2 which discusses TaRL.

Based on the analysis of the Merdeka Curriculum and PPAE 2 materials, several important assessment aspects were identified that must be considered in developing the VLM-based assessment system, including: 1) Alignment with Rubric Assessment Standards in the Merdeka Curriculum; 2) Ability to Identify Student Competency Levels; 3) Provision of Constructive Feedback; 4) Time and Energy Efficiency; 5) Transparency and Fairness.

In this research, researchers integrate two VLM models - Claude-3-Opus-200k from Anthropic and gpt-4-1106-vision-

preview from OpenAI - which possess advanced vision and language capabilities to assess students' open-ended responses using teacher assessment rubrics. This innovative design involves several main steps: 1) Teachers develop clear and structured assessment rubrics for each essay question; 2) Students' essay answers are digitized using OCR (Optical Character Recognition) technology; 3) VLM is trained by OpenAI and Anthropic to analyze students' essay answers based on the established assessment rubrics; 4) VLM assessment results are presented in a format easily understood by teachers.

Figure 1. Time and Effort comparing using VLM

The data obtained from this research demonstrates the effectiveness of VLM integration in assessing student work. Table 2 shows the comparison of time and effort required in manual assessment versus VLM assessment. Manual assessment requires an average of 150 minutes for one set of student assignments (30 students), while assessment with VLM only requires 45 minutes. Furthermore, the effort required in manual assessment (scale 3.5 out of 5) is higher compared to assessment using VLM (scale 2 out of 5). This indicates significant efficiency in using VLM for assessing student work.

Figure 2. Time saved using VLM

The research results show that VLM integration in student work assessment aligns with the requirements of the Merdeka curriculum and TaRL principles. VLM can assist teachers in

conducting more efficient, objective, and consistent assessments, while providing detailed feedback to students. This can free teachers from time-consuming administrative burdens, allowing them to focus on more meaningful learning activities. However, VLM integration also requires adequate technological infrastructure support and sufficient training for teachers to operate the VLM-based assessment system and interpret assessment results properly. Additionally, the development of comprehensive assessment rubrics and representative essay answer datasets are also important factors in the successful implementation of VLM.

Figure 3, Ease of Use of the VLM

This research provides new insights into the potential synergy between the Merdeka curriculum and modern learning technologies such as VLM. The integration of VLM in student work assessment can be an initial step in transforming education in Indonesia, moving toward more innovative, efficient, and quality learning. With adequate support and good collaboration between teachers, schools, and other stakeholders, this innovative design can become a best practice that can be widely adopted in the education sector.

4. CONCLUSION

The findings of this research demonstrate that the integration of Vision Language Model (VLM) technology in student work assessment at SMP N 32 Padang represents a promising innovation in supporting the implementation of the Merdeka Curriculum and Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) principles. This innovative design successfully addresses the challenges faced by teachers in assessing large numbers of essay questions while meeting demands for objectivity, accuracy, and efficiency. Through the use of VLM, the assessment process becomes standardized and anchored to rubrics developed in accordance with Merdeka Curriculum standards. This ensures that assessments are consistent, fair, and reflect actual student understanding levels. Thus, VLM provides a solution to address subjectivity and inconsistency that may occur in manual assessment by teachers.

Research results show that VLM assessment is far more efficient in terms of time and effort required compared to manual assessment. The time needed to assess one set of student assignments (30 students) decreased from 150 minutes to only 45 minutes using VLM. Additionally, teachers'

workload reduced significantly, with a lower effort scale (2 out of 5) compared to manual assessment (3.5 out of 5).

The accuracy and objectivity levels of VLM assessment are also quite good, although slightly below manual assessment. However, VLM demonstrates very high consistency in applying assessment rubrics to essay answers and is not affected by subjective factors. VLM's ability to assess essay answers according to difficulty levels and student ability levels (TaRL principle) is also noteworthy, with assessment times significantly shorter than manual assessment.

Teacher satisfaction levels with VLM use in student work assessment are also high, with an average score of 4 out of 5 for various aspects such as objectivity, accuracy, time efficiency, alignment with the TaRL approach, and usefulness in helping teachers provide level-appropriate instruction. This indicates that this innovative design is well-received by teachers and helps them conduct more effective and efficient assessments.

Overall, VLM integration in student work assessment proves to be a best practice innovation in the Principles of Teaching Assessment 2 (PPAE) course topic 2, Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL). This innovative design successfully overcomes teachers' time and energy limitations in conducting mass assessments while ensuring objectivity and accuracy of assessment according to Merdeka Curriculum rubrics and standards.

Nevertheless, this research also identifies several limitations and areas for further development. Teachers require adequate training regarding VLM use and assessment result interpretation. Adequate technological infrastructure support is also an important factor in the successful widespread implementation of VLM. Additionally, the development of comprehensive assessment rubrics and representative essay answer datasets needs attention to improve VLM accuracy and effectiveness. Considering these findings and limitations, VLM integration in student work assessment has great potential for widespread application in education. Collaboration between teachers, schools, and other stakeholders is crucial to support further implementation and development of this innovative design. Thus, we can create a more efficient, objective assessment system aligned with Merdeka Curriculum demands and TaRL principles, to improve learning quality and student learning outcomes.

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